

CMIP DATA ACCESS TASK TEAM

Data Access Task Team White Paper

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Introduction

This document distills information gathered by the CMIP Data Access Task Team for use by the CMIP Panel, the WCRP Infrastructure Panel, and other interested readers. The team was tasked with identifying barriers to the provisioning, distribution, and use of CMIP data. In particular the task team chose not to propose solutions given that the prioritization of problems and the technical and/or organizational expertise to evaluate possible responses were both outside the team's expertise. The task team does note that opportunities exist to refine both technical, organizational, and financial aspect of the system.

The sections below describe the state of play during CMIP6 and then the barriers identified by the task team for data production, dissemination, and access respectively. Progress made for CMIP7 is described and a coda reviews alternative paths taken by another, much smaller, WCRP project.

Background

Task team history

The CMIP panel's Data Access Task team [see Appendix] was established in February 2023 to identify barriers to the efficient use of CMIP data, with a related interest in understanding barriers to provisioning CMIP-compatible data. Team membership (detailed at the document's end) included a cross-section of members primarily interested in data provision, data distribution, and data use. Members spanned academic, technical, non-governmental, and business fields.

The team met six times between February 2023 and January 2024, during which the team heard from other team members and external speakers. Here the team provides a synthesis of raised by speakers and during internal discussions, organized around themes that emerged from discussion. Meetings devoted to particular subjects sometimes drew on stakeholder groups. A more formal but similar process focused on the research community and the role of centralized data stores was undertaken in the UK; their synthesis report is available at [doi:10.5281/zenodo.15680793](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15680793).

CMIP data: standardization and value for diverse communities

Much of the value of CMIP data arises from its standardization including the experimental protocols and especially the data formats. Standardized output facilitates consistent comparisons across diverse models from institutions worldwide, which is seen as enhancing the reliability and reproducibility of climate research. CMIP was an early leader in emphasizing open data and transparency, making its datasets freely available to non-commercial researchers globally, which has enabled broad participation and interdisciplinary applications. This accessibility is particularly important for regions or organizations with limited computational infrastructure or data management capabilities.

CMIP data attracts a diverse range of end-users from various fields, each with distinct goals, expertise, and requirements. These profiles reflect the broad applicability of climate model data across disciplines and sectors. Below are the primary categories of CMIP data end-users:

User group	Proficiency level	Purpose/Usage of CMIP data	Tools
Climate Scientists/Researchers	Advanced	Conduct climate modelling, process understanding, and model validation.	Work with original (if reformatted) data, HPC and/or cloud systems, specialized tools like xarray, CDO, Linux, Python.
Educational Institutions/Students	Basic to Advanced	Teach/learn climate science concepts, complete research projects.	Students: Learn to use raw data for projects. Instructors/Researchers: Teach and publish.
Private Sector	Intermediate to Advanced	Assess climate risks to business operations, supply chains, and infrastructure.	Analyze and tailor data for climate risks; use GIS, impact models, and business strategies.
Policy Makers/ Government/NGOs /Advocacy Groups	Basic to intermediate	Inform policy decisions, develop mitigation/adaptation strategies, and risk assessments.	Use processed/visualized data for decision-making, occasionally employ GIS tools.

Table 1 profiles of CMIP data users

Each group interacts with CMIP data differently, depending on their technical expertise and goals or expectations. This compounds the technical complexity of producing, distributing and managing CMIP information.

CMIP data standards have remained relatively stable over the last several project phases: data is provided as single-variable netCDF files with metadata building on the CF (Climate and Forecast) conventions supplemented with many detailed metadata attributes. Consistent standards have encouraged the development of tool ecosystems (e.g. Python libraries such as xgcm which build on more general-purpose packages like xarray; command line tools such as the Climate Data Operators). Nonetheless working with CMIP data (as with other large, complex, or diverse set of data) presents a steep learning curve for new users, as they must not only acquire proficiency in these tools but also develop workflows for handling large, complex datasets.

The scale of CMIP data presents another challenge. CMIP6 produced datasets on the scale of tens of petabytes, reflecting the increased resolution and complexity of models, as well as the diverse scenarios and experiments undertaken. This posed significant technical challenges including ensuring data integrity and enabling efficient access. The sheer size of the data often requires the use of large-scale computing resources.

Organizational confluences

The form of the data provided by modelling centres for CMIP is influenced by many standards and conventions including

- CF conventions that define aspects of the data and metadata (e.g. variable names, units, and attributes)
- the CMIP data request that specifies in detail which data is to be produced by which experiments.

Conformity (always imperfect and/or incomplete) with these standards is supported or relied on by

- CMIP controlled vocabularies which ensure consistency in data and metadata across contributions
- The WCRP Infrastructure Panel which coordinates across these and other issues
- And especially the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) by which data is distributed.

Many data access issues come to a head in the ESGF, as described more fully below. The ESGF is both a decentralized network of data nodes hosted by institutions worldwide and the organization responsible for those nodes. The standardized software aims to provide modelling centres with the ability to make available, curate, and manage model outputs while maintaining high standards of quality and compliance with CMIP protocols. For users, ESGF seeks to provide efficient distribution and access to the enormous datasets, along with search capabilities exploiting the rich metadata to allow users to find relevant datasets more efficiently.

ESGF explicitly seeks to foster collaboration, acting to facilitate knowledge exchange and capacity-building through forums, training sessions, and workshops. ESGF also seeks to enable researchers to work together across institutional and geographic boundaries by providing data and tools necessary to understand and address global climate challenges.

Community responses for CMIP6

The scale and value of CMIP6 data inspired several approaches aimed at augmenting data distribution by the ESGF. These included

- National-scale efforts (most notably at Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison (PCMDI) in the US, the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis in the UK and the Climate Computing Centre [DKRZ] in Germany) to build centralized archives of CMIP output co-located with computing resources
- A subset of CMIP6 is redistributed by the Copernicus Climate Change Service via the Data Store as an operational service

- Several grass-roots efforts organized by the Pangeo community to reproducibly ingest and reformat CMIP data in publicly accessible storage on commercial cloud services (e.g. Google Cloud, Amazon Web Services). Generous storage was provided *pro bono* by the commercial entities as a way of attracting customers for computing resources.

Barriers to production

Some challenges in the production and distribution of compliant data are shared by modelling centres contributing to CMIP and by small groups of researchers or other entities who would like to leverage CMIP protocols, standards, and infrastructure in their own projects.

Automated tests for standards compliance are limited

The ESGF software stack includes automated tools (e.g. QA-DKRZ, CF-checker) for data validation during the publication process. These tools flag errors in metadata or formatting, ensuring that datasets meet minimum compliance standards before being made available.

The many interlocking layers of standards and protocols mean that the tools do not ensure a 100% compliance and fault free catalogue. Compliance was originally achieved using a software tool (the Climate Model Output Rewriter, or CMOR) developed at PCMDI; the ability to reproduce CMOR output has become the *de facto* standard since no toolchain covers the entire scope of requirements for either production or validation.

Compliance verification tools themselves require development and maintenance, but these tasks have no obvious home. Reducing the number of redundant tools currently available to the strictly necessary, viable minimum quality assurance, ideally through running a single universal framework, can help alleviate the confusion.

The non-trivial costs of compliance checking, and the costs of correcting non-compliant data, are often an afterthought when scoping CMIP requirements in modelling centres. It has been common for data node managers to skip on checks and data assurance scripts for resources constraints, including time, people power or simply understanding and acting on the warning and error messages.

The tools are not designed for use outside the ESGF and so can't be easily used by smaller groups seeking to produce data conforming to CMIP standards but potentially distributed outside the ESGF.

Barriers to distribution

The Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) is both a set of **software** tools enabling decentralized data distribution and the **organization** that develops and manages both the tools themselves and the computing and data systems providing data.

ESGF plays two distinct roles. Data is “published” by individual modelling centres/ESGF nodes, which announce the availability of data. This set of announcements forms the basis for complete catalogues of data. In addition some nodes (notably PCMDI in the US, CEDA in the UK, and DKRZ in Germany in

CMIP6) also replicate data provided by other nodes and hence appear to users as centralized resources for data, much as content delivery networks or edge nodes do outside the research context.

Organizational hurdles

The ESGF operates as a collaborative, decentralized community that supports CMIP data distribution. It is a federation of numerous institutions and organizations that contribute time and resources to develop and maintain the required tools for the validation, publication and archiving of the data and metadata.

Because the ESGF community operates on a voluntary basis, with participation from various participants across the globe, the organization has a horizontal structure that relies on collaboration and equality among participants. Decision making is distributed and the access is open to any entity that wants to contribute. There is, in other words, no centralized control, no single, authoritative governing body that can impose uniform standards or resolve disputes quickly. This potentially leads to slow decision making, fragmented policies and limited accountability. These symptoms are often reflected in the data quality and standardization issues for downstream users.

Financial challenges

The dependency on the voluntary contributions of researchers, institutions and organizations also results in some financial issues. Mostly a lack of long-term commitment, as actors may stop contributing to ESGF if their priorities change, leading to gaps in data availability or access over time. This uneven data availability also contributes to the unbalanced access for some regions or modelling centres.

Today, the ESGF effort is supported by multiple streams of financing depending on the entities. But it is structured mainly through two different models. On the US side, the DoE (Department of Energy) picks a lead laboratory to receive the financing and organize US contributions. On the European side, and after the end of the IS-ENES project (e-infrastructure of the European Network for Earth System Modelling) that played a similar central role in funding contributions counter-balancing the DoE, multiple EU level projects support ESGF activities (e.g. Copernicus), however these are much shorter in timeline and have specific needs that can sometimes not be aligned with the ESGF timeline.

There is little involvement from Asia and none from commercial organizations or industry. A common theme in task team meetings was that reducing barriers to entry would enable increased uptake and involvement from third party actors (cloud providers, private and public users, smaller projects) to invest in the existing tools and infrastructure instead of building on top of it or to the side.

Bridging the gap: Progress and challenges in a changing CMIP technical ecosystem

Since the Data Access Task Team last convened, both the technical instances under the WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel and the CMIP International Project Office (IPO) have advanced in preparing the technical landscape for the upcoming CMIP7 exercise. This white paper documents user experiences from CMIP6 across the production, storage, discovery, and access chain. Due to its delayed release, however, its findings will not influence the tools and systems already established for CMIP7.

That said, many of the challenges and hurdles identified in this report were already recognized by the community. This section highlights ongoing efforts to address these issues and improve the situation.

Data production

The **CMOR tool** remains a cornerstone requirement for climate modelling groups, ensuring standardized model output and compliance with the Data Request and Controlled Vocabularies Task Teams' specifications—a critical step for maintaining inter-comparability. While most groups rely on CMOR as a post-processing tool, some, such as the IPSL modelling centre, have integrated these requirements directly into their coupler component (XIOS), a practice that could serve as a model for broader adoption.

In the data distribution pipeline, **netCDF files** will now undergo an additional **repacking step** of the B-tree nodes before release (see the figure below). This process reorganizes file structure to optimize partial access, improving efficiency for users retrieving specific data subsets.

This figure shows the distribution of B-tree nodes of the different netCDF variables (byte offsets on the x-axis, measured in MB) for both an unpacked and a repacked netCDF file. B-tree nodes in the unpacked file are scattered throughout the netCDF file (about 120 MB). In contrast, in the repacked file, the B-tree nodes are located within the first 120 KB of the file (0.12 MB). As a result, they can be retrieved in a single HTTP range request.

Quality control has been streamlined under a single, user-friendly tool that consolidates checks, simplifies reporting, and enhances reusability for other Model Intercomparison

Projects (MIPs). This includes a revamped approach to **vocabulary control** embedded directly into the publication software stack.

Data distribution and discovery

The **ESGF federated architecture** has been replaced by a more resilient system: the data catalogue/index will be hosted at two transatlantic locations using the **SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) standard**, with data publication managed via a **Kafka messaging queue**. This design eliminates inconsistencies that previously arose between original and replica datasets—such as mismatched metadata or file hashes—ensuring both indexes serve as the definitive source of truth. The messaging queue also enables real-time updates for downstream tools, including download and replication robots, which can now maintain up-to-date local archives for national computing clusters or initiatives like Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S).

To bridge the gap between scientific knowledge and structured controlled vocabularies, the community has developed esgvoc.ipsl.fr, a resource designed to help users navigate and understand the terminology essential for effective data discovery.

Data download

Finally, the **wget download process**, which has historically demanded significant user support, will be phased out in favour of **esgpull**, a community-developed tool designed for greater reliability and ease of use.

While these advancements mark substantial progress in user experience across the data chain, challenges remain—particularly in **server-side computing** which remains best addressed through localized projects leveraging the proposed infrastructure.

Changing contexts

The scope of CMIP has grown enormously in the roughly 20 years since CMIP3 and the user experience of identifying data has become somewhat more streamlined. The core model for data distribution, however – the downloading of painstakingly formatted individual files – has not changed. The advantage of continuity has been that relatively little conceptual effort needs to be expended in each phase by analysts using the data (or by modelling centres in producing it) and that comparison across phases of CMIP is relatively straightforward. The consistency has also provided a common language for climate model data that is leveraged by other projects.

The CMIP approach informed another WCRP project: the Digital Earths Lighthouse Activity and its effort to exploit very high-resolution (“km-scale”) data. The Lighthouse Activity convened a data analysis hackathon in May 2025 that made available data from roughly ten global simulations. Relative to CMIP these made use of

- Data provided in Zarr stores (data arrays in text format), providing access to all variables from a given simulation via one access point
- Data available via streaming protocols such as Amazon S3, allowing users to access the data without downloading the Zarr stores
- Data discovery via Python-language intake catalogs, allowing programmatic references to data
- Data stored on the HEALPix equal-area grid, with all resolutions accessible in the same Zarr store, allowing analysis at variable resolution.

This approach aimed to lower some of the same barriers to data access identified by the task team. In particular the collection of technologies allowed users to access the precise subset of data they needed by referencing a the single authoritative copy of the data.

On the other hand, preparing the data for the hackathon took enormous technical effort across all contributing modelling centres – not less than that required for producing CMIP data. The audience for the hackathon data was a tiny fraction of that using CMIP data and the data, though voluminous, are much less complicated. Whether any aspects of this approach might be adapted for CMIP remains an open question.

Appendices

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Former members

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